

Dispersive solid phase extraction of β -blockers from water samples using a graphene oxide aerogel followed by liquid chromatography mass spectrometry analysis

Androniki Rapti^{a,b}, Konstantinos Maroulas^c, Eleni Evgenidou^{d,e}, Vasileios Alampanos^{d,e}, George Kyzas^c, Dimitrios N. Bikiaris^b, Dimitra A. Lambropoulou^{d,e,*}

^a School of Science and Technology, Hellenic Open University (HOU), GR-26335, Patra, Greece

^b Laboratory of Polymer and Colors Chemistry and Technology, Department of Chemistry, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, 54124, Greece

^c Hephaestus Laboratory, School of Chemistry, Faculty of Sciences, Democritus University of Thrace (DUTH), GR-654 04 Kavala, Greece

^d Laboratory of Environmental Pollution Control, Department of Chemistry, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, GR-54124 Thessaloniki, Greece

^e Centre for Interdisciplinary Research and Innovation (CIRI-AUTH), Balkan Center, Thessaloniki, 10th km Thessaloniki-Thermi Rd, GR 57001, Greece

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Dispersive solid phase extraction
B-Blockers
Graphene oxide aerogel
Water samples analysis
Sample preparation

ABSTRACT

A newly developed dispersive solid-phase extraction (d-SPE) method was established for the determination of β -blockers in environmental water samples using a biopolymer-based aerogel composed of chitosan (CS), polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), and reduced graphene oxide (rGO). Initially, four aerogel materials with varying GO and rGO content were synthesized and evaluated to identify the most efficient sorbent. The aerogel containing 5 % rGO exhibited the highest extraction performance and was selected for method development. Sorbents were characterized by FTIR, SEM, and BET analyses. Extraction conditions including sorbent amount, extraction time, and sample pH, were optimized to maximize efficiency. The final method, coupled with liquid chromatography–mass spectrometry, enabled the determination of six β -blockers. The aerogel's high surface area (949 m²/g), suitable pore structure (1.38 nm), and abundance of functional groups facilitated hydrogen bonding, π – π interactions, and electrostatic adsorption, enhancing extraction performance. The performance of the method was evaluated by determining key analytical parameters in five different water matrices, namely in drinking water, lake water, marine water, river water, as well as in influent and effluent wastewater. The method's environmental impact was assessed using the ComplexMoGAPI index, achieving a score of 75, thereby meeting the criteria for green analytical methods. Additional evaluations using the Blue Applicability Grade Index (BAGI) and Violet Innovation Grade Index (VIGI) further confirmed the method's practicality and novelty. Overall, the proposed approach offers a sensitive, reproducible, and sustainable workflow for the routine monitoring of β -blockers in diverse environmental water matrices.

1. Introduction

Pharmaceuticals and personal care products (PPCPs) are often excreted from the human body with minimal alteration to their chemical structure, leading to their frequent detection in urban wastewater, from which they can disperse into other environmental matrices [1]. The increasing presence of PPCPs in aquatic environments poses a significant threat to ecosystems and human health due to their concentration-related adverse effects. Many PPCPs, including beta-blockers (β -blockers), are classified as emerging contaminants due to their

widespread use, persistence in the environment, incomplete removal during wastewater treatment, and potential ecological impacts [2]. β -Blockers are well-known antihypertensive agents, widely prescribed for cardiovascular disorders. They are frequently found in wastewater effluents, surface waters, and even drinking water highlight their ubiquity in aquatic systems [3–6]. Their persistence and insufficient removal lead to accumulation in various matrices, including environmental matrices and living organisms, as well. [5,6]. Furthermore, β -blockers disrupt the physiological processes of aquatic organisms by targeting adrenergic receptors, which are conserved across many

* Corresponding author at: Laboratory of Environmental Pollution Control, Department of Chemistry, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, GR-54124 Thessaloniki, Greece.

E-mail address: dlambro@chem.auth.gr (D.A. Lambropoulou).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.microc.2025.114531>

Received 3 June 2025; Received in revised form 7 July 2025; Accepted 8 July 2025

Available online 10 July 2025

0026-265X/© 2025 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

species, posing significant ecotoxicological risks [3,6]. Thus, the extraction and determination of β -blockers from water samples have become a critical issue.

To that end, liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) is a leading and highly efficient analytical technique [4,7,8]. However, sample preparation remains the cornerstone of any analytical method due to the need for sample cleanup, preconcentration of analytes typically present at trace levels, handling complex matrices, and eliminating matrix interferences to protect instrumental equipment while enhancing sensitivity and accuracy [9]. Conventional sample preparation techniques, such as solid-phase extraction (SPE) and liquid-liquid extraction (LLE), are regularly employed for extracting β -blockers [4,7,8,10–12]. However, these techniques, although efficient, are associated with certain limitations that conflict with the principles of Green Analytical Chemistry (GAC) [13]. These principles have had an unprecedented influence on the field of sample preparation, driving new trends such as the development of innovative sample preparation techniques, the miniaturization of existing methods and experimental setups, the adoption of green solvent alternatives, the automation of processes, the reduction of solvent and sorbent usage, the exploration of novel materials with advanced properties, and the incorporation of naturally derived or bio-based sorbent materials [9,13,14]. Furthermore, efforts are being made to develop sorbents that can be reused or recycled, enhancing sustainability and aligning these methodologies more closely with the goals of GAC. Many of these advances have already been adopted for determining β -blockers in biological samples [15]. However, for environmental samples, only a few methods have been established, primarily utilizing dispersive solid-phase extraction (d-SPE) in combination with a limited range of novel materials [16–19].

d-SPE has emerged as a more efficient alternative sample preparation technique, offering enhanced analyte recovery, reduced solvent consumption, and compatibility with advanced and green sorbent materials [14,15]. Additionally, it is an easy-to-apply method, making it highly accessible for various analytical applications. The modus operandi of d-SPE involves dispersing a sorbent into the liquid sample, promoting rapid interaction with analytes through intermolecular interactions depending on the sorbent and analytes. This ensures selective adsorption of target compounds. The dispersed sorbent's high surface area accelerates adsorption, and after extraction, the sorbent with the adsorbed analytes is separated by centrifugation or filtration. The analytes are then eluted using a suitable solvent. This efficient, low-waste process supports the use of green and reusable sorbents, aligning with GAC, while offering adaptability and sustainability.

The development of advanced adsorbent materials has revolutionized d-SPE methodologies [14,15,20,21]. Graphene oxide (GO), with its high surface area, tunable functional groups (epoxy, hydroxyl and carboxyl), strong adsorption capacity, and modification potential, has gained attention for its application in analytical method development [16,22]. Interestingly, when graphene oxide is formed in the configuration of aerogel is even more efficient since aerogel have porous 3D nature, open-geometry structure, even more increased surface areal while they are handier and versatile [23]. Furthermore, the incorporation of biopolymers into graphene oxide aerogels enhances their mechanical stability, compatibility with diverse matrices, extraction efficiency and selectivity, making the final sorbents suitable for green extraction of pharmaceutical residues in environmental analysis [20,23–25]. Chitosan is a well-known biopolymer with advantageous properties [26]. Despite these, limited research has explored the combination of biopolymers with graphene oxide aerogels specifically for the extraction of β -blockers from environmental water samples.

In this study, we present a novel approach utilizing biopolymer chitosan-graphene oxide aerogel-based dispersive solid-phase extraction for the efficient isolation six of β -blockers, namely atenolol, pindolol, timolol, metoprolol, bisoprolol, propranolol (see Table 1) from water samples. Four sorptive aerogel materials were synthesized and tested to determine the most effective one for the sample preparation workflow.

The final protocol was coupled with liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry, enabling highly sensitive and selective detection. This study focuses on optimizing critical parameters to enhance extraction efficiency, validating the developed method, and evaluating its green chemistry credentials using the ComplexMoGAPI index [27]. Additionally, the method's applicability is demonstrated across various environmental matrices, including seawater, river water, and wastewater effluent and influent. By integrating innovative material science with advanced analytical techniques, this research offers a sustainable and effective solution for monitoring pharmaceutical contaminants in aquatic environments.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Reagents and chemicals

The β -blockers targeted in this study are presented in Table 1. Analytical standards for these compounds were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (Steinheim, Germany). All chemicals used were of analytical or HPLC grade to minimize interference during analysis. LC-MS grade methanol (MeOH), acetonitrile (ACN), and formic acid ($\geq 99\%$ purity) were purchased from Thermo Fisher Scientific (Waltham, MA, USA). Chitosan powder (medium molecular weight, 75–85% deacetylated) and graphene oxide (GO) were obtained from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). Stock solutions of each β -blocker (1000 mg/L) were prepared in methanol and stored at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in amber glass bottles to prevent photodegradation. Working solutions were freshly prepared by diluting the stock solutions with appropriate solvents prior to each experiment. All solutions were prepared using ultrapure water (resistivity: 18.2 M Ω -cm) generated by a Milli-Q-Plus ultra-pure water system (Merck, Germany).

2.2. Synthesis of aerogel sorbents

The synthesis process was conducted using a modified sol-gel method to obtain stable and porous aerogels with optimal sorptive properties. The procedure was as follows:

A chitosan (CS) solution (1% w/v) was prepared by dissolving chitosan powder in distilled water acidified with 2% (v/v) acetic acid under continuous stirring until complete dissolution was achieved. Separately, polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) powder was dissolved in distilled water at $80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and stirred for 16 h to produce a 1% (w/v) PVA solution. Graphene oxide (GO) and reduced graphene oxide (rGO) solutions were prepared by dispersing GO and rGO flakes in water, followed by ultrasonication until complete dissolution was achieved. The CS solution and the PVA solution were then combined in a defined ratio and stirred thoroughly. This procedure was repeated three more times, yielding four solutions with a CS/PVA ratio of 2:1. Next, GO and rGO solutions were added to the respective mixtures and stirred until homogeneous. Four distinct solutions were prepared as follows: (A) CS/PVA/GO solutions with (i) GO ratios of 2:1:0.02 (GO1%) and (ii) 2:1:0.1 (GO5%), (B) CS/PVA/rGO solutions with rGO ratios of (iii) 2:1:0.02 (rGO1%) and (iv) 2:1:0.1 (rGO5%). Subsequently, glutaraldehyde (GLA) (50% in H₂O) was added to each solution as a crosslinking agent, followed by continuous stirring until the mixtures transitioned into a gel phase. The resulting gels were frozen for 24 h to ensure structural stabilization. Freeze-drying was performed at $-104\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 48 h to produce aerogels with enhanced porosity and mechanical stability. Finally, the aerogels were purified by Soxhlet extraction with a water/methanol mixture for 24 h to remove unreacted reagents and impurities. In total, four distinct aerogel materials were synthesized, each designed to evaluate the impact of GO and rGO concentrations on extraction performance. The aerogel materials were stored in sealed, airtight containers at ambient temperature in a desiccator to prevent moisture absorption. No inert atmosphere (e.g., N₂) was required, but storage under dry conditions was essential to maintain the porous structure and specific surface area. Over a period of 3 months, no significant change in extraction efficiency

Table 1
Physicochemical data of interest of the examined β -blockers.

Name	Structure	CAS Number	Molecular Weight (g/mole)	logP	pKa	m/z	Chemical Formula	Solubility in water (mg/L, 25 °C)	Pharmacology
Atenolol		29,122-68-7	266.34	0.16	9.6	267.16	C ₁₄ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₃	13,300	Beta-blocker used to treat cardiovascular diseases
Pindolol		13,523-86-9	248.32	1.91	9.2	249.32	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	7880	Beta-blocker with intrinsic sympathomimetic activity
Timolol		26,839-75-8	316.42	1.6	9.2	317.16	C ₁₃ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₃ S	2740	Non-selective beta-adrenergic antagonist
Metoprolol		51,384-51-1	267.36	1.88	9.7	268.17	C ₁₅ H ₂₅ NO ₃	16,900	Beta-1 selective adrenergic receptor blocker
Bisoprolol		66,722-44-9	325.44	1.35	9.6	326.14	C ₁₈ H ₃₁ NO ₄ S		Beta-blocker with high selectivity for beta-1 adrenergic receptors
Propranolol		525-66-6	259.34	3.48	9.4	260.15	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ NO ₂		Non-selective beta-blocker commonly used to treat hypertension

was observed, confirming the material's structural and functional stability under these conditions.

2.3. Characterization of aerogel sorbents

The synthesized aerogel sorbents were characterized using various analytical techniques to assess their structural and morphological properties. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) spectra were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer Spectrum One FTIR spectrometer with KBr disks as the sample matrix. The spectra were obtained in absorbance mode over the spectral range of 400–4000 cm^{-1} with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} , and each spectrum was the result of 64 co-added scans to ensure accurate spectral data. The morphology of the aerogels was examined using a JEOL JMS-840 A scanning electron microscope (SEM) equipped with an Oxford ISIS 300 energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) system. To prevent charging effects under the electron beam, all samples were coated with carbon black prior to imaging. Textural properties such as specific surface area, total pore volume, and pore size distribution were determined through nitrogen adsorption/desorption experiments at $-196\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The BET (Brunauer-Emmett-Teller) method was applied for surface area calculations, while the BJH (Barrett-Joyner-Halenda) method was used for pore size distribution analysis. Prior to these measurements, samples were outgassed at $80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 20 h under a vacuum of 6.6×10^{-9} mbar using an Autosorb-1MP Automatic Volumetric Sorption Analyzer (Quantachrome Instruments).

2.4. Dispersive solid phase extraction protocol

The optimum and most efficient d-SPE protocol was applied as follows: (1) 20 mg of the sorbent material was added to 20 mL of the sample solution; (2) the mixture was stirred for 15 min at 1000 rpm to facilitate the adsorption of the target compounds; (3) the sample was then centrifuged for 10 min at 5000 rpm to separate the sorbent from the liquid phase; (4) after centrifugation, the supernatant was carefully removed, and 500 μL of acetonitrile was added to the remaining sorbent; (5) elution was performed by placing the sample in an ultrasonic bath for 5 min to enhance the desorption of the analytes; (6) acetonitrile extract was collected and steps 4 and 5 were re-executed; (7) the acetonitrile extracts were collected and concentrated to 100 μL ; and finally, (7) the concentrated sample was introduced into the LC-MS system for analysis.

2.5. Instrumentation and chromatographic conditions

LC-MS analyses were performed using a Shimadzu SIL 20 A auto-sampler and a Shimadzu LC-20AB pump (Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan). Detection was conducted using a Shimadzu LC-MS-2010 EV mass selective detector (Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan) equipped with an electrospray ionization (ESI) source operating in positive ionization mode (ESI+). The nebulizing pressure was set to 100 psi, the capillary voltage was adjusted to 4500 V, and the fragmentation voltage was set to 1.65 V. Detection was performed using the Selected Ion Monitoring (SIM) mode, ensuring accurate identification and quantification of the targeted β -blockers. The sample injection volume was set to 20 μL . Chromatographic separation was achieved with a ZORBAX Eclipse XDB-C8 column (4.6 mm \times 150 mm \times 5 μm ; Agilent Technologies) maintained at $40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. A gradient elution program was employed using a binary mobile phase consisting of LC-MS grade water with 0.1 % formic acid (solvent A) and LC-MS grade methanol with 0.1 % formic acid (solvent B). The gradient profile started at 60 % A and 40 % B, followed by a linear decrease to 40 % A and 60 % B at 3 min. By 12 min, the mobile phase transitioned to 10 % A and 90 % B, which was maintained until 14 min. At this point, the mobile phase returned to its initial conditions of 60 % A and 40 % B, continuing until 20 min. The flow rate was kept constant at 0.4 mL/min throughout the analysis.

The retention times (t_{R}) and pseudo-molecular ions (m/z) of the

targeted β -blockers were as follows: Atenolol ($t_{\text{R}} = 4.11$ min, $m/z = 267$ $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^{+}$), Pindolol ($t_{\text{R}} = 4.53$ min, $m/z = 249$ $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^{+}$), Timolol ($t_{\text{R}} = 6.57$ min, $m/z = 317$ $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^{+}$), Metoprolol ($t_{\text{R}} = 6.66$ min, $m/z = 268$ $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^{+}$), Bisoprolol ($t_{\text{R}} = 7.77$ min, $m/z = 326$ $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^{+}$), and Propranolol ($t_{\text{R}} = 8.19$ min, $m/z = 260$ $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^{+}$). Fig. S1 illustrates a typical chromatogram demonstrating the efficiency of the developed method. This combination of gradient elution and SIM mode ensured the method's sensitivity, selectivity, and reliability for the detection and quantification of β -blockers in environmental water samples.

2.6. Method validation

The analytical method was validated following the guidelines of Commission Decision 2002/657/EC and Council Directive 96/23/EC, which outline the requirements for evaluating the performance of analytical methods and interpreting results. Additionally, the validation process was aligned with the standards of ISO/IEC 17025:2017, ensuring methodological reliability and compliance with international quality norms. To ensure the accuracy and robustness of the method, a series of validation tools were employed, including blank samples, standard solutions (calibration and test samples), spiked samples with known analyte concentrations, replicate measurements, and statistical analysis of the obtained data.

The identification and quantification of the target compounds in the samples were carried out in accordance with European Commission Decision 2002/657/EC and the guidelines set by DG SANTE 12682/2021. The qualitative identification of the compounds detected by LC-MS was based on multiple criteria: firstly, by matching the retention time of each compound in the sample with that of the corresponding standard, within a tolerance of ± 0.1 min; secondly, by examining the pseudo-molecular ions, and comparing their relative intensities in the sample to those observed in the standard solution (Fig. 7.2); and finally, by ensuring that any deviation in the relative intensity of the diagnostic ions did not exceed 30 %, provided the ion intensity in the reference standard was greater than 50 %.

The performance of the method was evaluated by determining key analytical parameters in five different water matrices, namely in drinking water, lake water, marine water, river water, as well as influent and effluent wastewater. Sensitivity was assessed through the calculation of the Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantification (LOQ) for each analyte. The LODs and LOQs were established based on the lowest concentrations of analyte that could be reliably detected and quantified, corresponding to signal-to-noise ratios (S/N) of 3 and 10, respectively. Linearity was evaluated to confirm the proportional relationship between analyte concentration and instrumental response across the calibration range. A five-point calibration curve was constructed using analyte concentrations spanning from the LOQ up to 1000 $\mu\text{g/L}$. Standard solutions were injected both prior to and following the sample extracts to ensure accuracy and consistency in quantification. Selectivity was also assessed by examining the chromatographic profiles of blank samples to ensure that no interfering peaks were present at the retention times of the analytes. The absence of such interferences confirmed the method's ability to selectively detect the target compounds in complex matrices. Accuracy describes the agreement between a measured result and the true value. In this study, it was evaluated by calculating percent recoveries at 100 $\mu\text{g/L}$, tested in triplicate. Blank samples were spiked with known analyte amounts, and recovery was calculated using: $\text{Recovery (\%)} = (\text{Response of analyte in the sample} / \text{Response of analyte in the standard}) \times 100$.

Precision was examined in terms of repeatability (RSD_r) and reproducibility (RSD_R), reflecting the consistency of results under repeat and varying conditions, respectively. Internal quality control was applied to each sample batch to ensure the stability and reliability of the analytical system. Repeatability refers to the method's ability to yield consistent results under the same conditions over a short period. In this study, repeatability was assessed by performing three replicate experiments at

two concentration levels (10 µg/L and 100 µg/L) within the same day. Results were expressed as the relative standard deviation of repeatability (RSDr), indicating short-term analytical precision. Reproducibility, on the other hand, evaluates the method's performance under variable conditions. It was determined by conducting three independent experiments at the same two concentration levels (10 µg/L and 100 µg/L) over three different days. The resulting relative standard deviation of reproducibility (RSDR) reflects the method's robustness over time and under different analytical sessions. Both parameters were calculated using standard statistical formulas, and the low RSDr and RSDR values confirmed the method's precision and reliability across experimental conditions. Internal quality control was applied to each sample batch to monitor the stability of the analytical system. During batch analysis, five-point calibration curves were prepared for all target compounds, and a blank sample was injected after every 20 samples to ensure ongoing system integrity. Additionally, two quality control (QC) samples, extracted at the LOQ level and at 10 times the LOQ, were injected every 20 samples within the same batch. After analysis, the concentrations measured in the blank samples were subtracted from those of the test samples, and the resulting recoveries were used to calculate the concentrations of the unknowns.

2.7. 2.8. Real sample collection

Water samples from various matrices were collected for analysis. Urban influent and effluent were sampled from the Wastewater Treatment Plant (WWTP) of Thessaloniki, located in Northern Greece. Marine water was obtained from the coastal area of Thessaloniki, while river water was collected from the Strymonas River, and lake water from lake Doirani. Drinking water samples were taken from the municipal water supply system of Thessaloniki, representative of treated tap water intended for human consumption. Upon arrival at the laboratory, all samples were stored in amber glass bottles at 4 °C. Before further processing, the samples were filtered through 0.45 µm membrane filters to remove particulate matter and prepare them for subsequent analysis.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization of adsorbents

3.1.1. FTIR analysis

The FTIR spectrum (Fig. 1) reveals several characteristic peaks corresponding to functional groups present in the synthesized aerogels. In the spectral region between 3000 and 3500 cm⁻¹, the broad peak

Fig. 1. FTIR spectra of the aerogel adsorbents.

observed corresponds to the presence of hydrophilic hydrogen bonds formed between nitrogen and oxygen atoms, which is consistent with previous studies [28–32]. The GO-derived materials exhibit a broader peak in this region compared to the rGO aerogels, indicating a higher concentration of these functional groups.

In the region around 2900 cm⁻¹, the peaks corresponding to symmetric and asymmetric C–H stretching vibrations are significantly enhanced in the rGO-derived aerogels. This increase suggests that rGO materials contain a greater number of hydrophobic regions, which aligns with previous observations [33,34]. The presence of amine I and amine II bands at 1650 cm⁻¹ and 1555 cm⁻¹, respectively, is attributed to chitosan and is crucial for the adsorption process [35]. The rGO-derived aerogels demonstrate a higher intensity for these peaks, indicating an increased availability of amine groups. This observation supports the hypothesis that the epoxide and carboxyl groups in GO reacted with the amine groups in chitosan via a nucleophilic addition reaction, subsequently converting primary –NH₂ groups into secondary imine (–NH) groups [29,36]. These spectral features confirm the successful incorporation of graphene derivatives and chitosan, while also explaining the distinct chemical characteristics and adsorption potential of the synthesized aerogels.

3.1.2. SEM analysis

SEM micrographs (Fig. 2) revealed that all aerogels exhibited a well-developed three-dimensional porous network with interconnected layers. The GO-derived aerogels displayed a smoother surface compared to their rGO counterparts and demonstrated a stacking structure composed of GO sheets with visible wrinkles. This structural feature indicates the successful dispersion of GO within the CS/PVA solution, which is attributed to the formation of strong hydrogen bonds between GO and the CS/PVA matrix [37,38]. In contrast, the rGO-derived aerogels exhibited a honeycomb-like structure characterized by a greater number of pores, larger pore sizes, and increased surface roughness. This distinctive morphology enhances the adsorption capacity of rGO-based materials. The incorporation of rGO resulted in an expanded porous network and increased interlayer spacing, further improving the material's surface accessibility and adsorption efficiency [39]. These morphological differences highlight the impact of graphene derivative selection on the structural properties of the synthesized aerogels, with rGO derivatives demonstrating improved porosity and textural characteristics conducive to enhanced adsorption performance.

3.1.3. Nitrogen adsorption-desorption and BET analysis

The specific surface area of the synthesized aerogels was determined by BET analysis, using nitrogen adsorption/desorption measurements conducted at 77 K (Fig. 3). Prior to analysis, all aerogel samples were degassed at 80 °C under vacuum for 20 h to remove any adsorbed moisture or impurities. The specific BET surface areas (*S*_{BET}) of the synthesized aerogels were evaluated within the relative pressure range of *P*/*P*₀ = 0.05 to 0.35. The results indicated that all aerogel materials exhibited a macroporous structure, consisting predominantly of macro- and micropores. The high specific surface areas observed can be attributed to the macroporous nature of the aerogels, as well as the presence of abundant active sites throughout the polymeric structure, as confirmed by FTIR analysis. Additionally, the increased roughness and surface irregularities observed in the SEM images further support the presence of a well-developed porous network. The nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms of all aerogels exhibited a Type III profile, indicative of a macroporous structure, according to the IUPAC classification. This adsorption behavior is associated with relatively weak adsorbent-adsorbate interactions, where adsorbed molecules tend to aggregate around the most energetically favorable sites on the macroporous solid's surface.

The pore size distribution (PSD) was derived from the BJH desorption model, revealing that the average pore diameter ranged from 1.38 to 2.28 nm (Fig. 4). Notably, the rGO-based aerogels demonstrated

Fig. 2. SEM micrographs of aerogel adsorbents.

higher S_{BET} values, confirming their superior adsorption capacity. Increasing the concentration of GO in the aerogel matrix resulted in a slight increase in pore volume (PV) and S_{BET} . Conversely, the addition of rGO significantly enhanced both S_{BET} and PV, with the rGO5% aerogel achieving the highest values among the tested sorbent materials [Table 2](#).

3.1.4. Selected aerogel sorbent: rGO5%/PVA/chitosan aerogel

The rGO5%/PVA/chitosan aerogel demonstrates superior performance as a sorbent material due to its advantageous structural properties. It exhibits the highest BET surface area among the tested materials, reaching $949 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$, which provides a greater number of active sites for adsorption. This increased surface area significantly enhances the material's ability to capture and retain contaminants. In addition to its extensive surface area, rGO5% also possesses the largest pore volume ($0.73 \text{ cm}^3/\text{g}$), promoting improved diffusion of analytes and ensuring better accessibility to active sites. The aerogel's pore size distribution is another key factor, with an average pore size of 1.38 nm , which is ideal for accommodating smaller molecules such as β -blockers while still maintaining efficient fluid transport through the porous network. The enhanced properties of reduced graphene oxide (rGO) further improve adsorption capacity, as rGO is known for its superior conductivity, increased surface defects, and additional functional groups that strengthen molecular interactions. The pronounced surface roughness observed in SEM images further confirms the improved structural characteristics of rGO5%, underscoring its suitability as an effective sorbent material. Overall, the rGO5% aerogel is the most efficient

material in terms of surface area, pore volume, and adsorption potential, making it the best-performing sorbent for environmental water sample purification and β -blocker extraction.

3.2. Extraction mechanism and intermolecular interactions

The extraction process operates on an equilibrium-driven model, where the distribution of analytes between the sample solution and the sorbent surface is influenced by their polarity and functional groups. The strength of this affinity determines whether the analyte remains in the solution or migrates toward the sorbent. The extraction mechanism is controlled by a combination of intermolecular forces, including van der Waals forces, dipole-dipole interactions, ionic bonds, π - π interactions, and hydrophobic interactions, all of which contribute to the overall adsorption efficiency.

The rGO5% aerogel possesses a variety of functional groups that facilitate strong interactions with β -blockers. These functional groups, originating from both the reduced graphene oxide (rGO) and chitosan/PVA components, include hydroxyl ($-\text{OH}$), carboxyl ($-\text{COOH}$), epoxide ($-\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C}$), amine ($-\text{NH}_2$), and imine ($-\text{NH}$) groups, as well as aromatic π -systems from the graphitic carbon structure and hydrophobic domains. The presence of these functional groups allows multiple types of interactions to occur between rGO5% and β -blockers, enhancing its adsorption capacity.

Among these interactions, π - π interactions play a significant role due to the presence of aromatic rings in β -blockers such as propranolol and

Fig. 3. Nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms of GO and rGO aerogels.

pindolol. These molecules interact strongly with the delocalized π -electron system in the graphene structure, promoting effective adsorption. Additionally, hydrogen bonding is another key mechanism, occurring between the $-\text{OH}$ and $-\text{COOH}$ groups in rGO and the amine or hydroxyl groups present in β -blockers like atenolol and metoprolol. The effectiveness of hydrogen bonding interactions is closely linked to the presence of hydrogen bond donors and hydrogen bond acceptors. The rGO5% aerogel contains abundant hydroxyl ($-\text{OH}$) and carboxyl ($-\text{COOH}$) groups, both of which can act as hydrogen bond donors by providing hydrogen atoms capable of forming hydrogen bonds with suitable acceptors in β -blocker molecules. These functional groups also serve as hydrogen bond acceptors through their oxygen atoms, facilitating interactions with the hydrogen-containing moieties of β -blockers. β -blockers such as atenolol, metoprolol, and propranolol possess hydroxyl groups ($-\text{OH}$) and amine groups ($-\text{NH}_2$) that function as hydrogen bond donors, forming strong interactions with oxygen atoms in the $-\text{COOH}$ and $-\text{OH}$ groups on the rGO5% surface. Conversely, the oxygen atoms in the β -blockers' hydroxyl, ether, and amide groups can act as hydrogen bond acceptors, effectively interacting with the hydrogen atoms present in the rGO's $-\text{OH}$ and $-\text{NH}$ groups.

The presence of amine groups in chitosan further enables electrostatic interactions, particularly under acidic conditions where chitosan becomes positively charged and interacts with negatively charged

$-\text{COO}^-$ groups in rGO or protonated β -blockers such as propranolol in its $[\text{R}-\text{NH}_3]^+$ form. Furthermore, hydrophobic interactions between the non-functionalized graphitic regions of rGO and the non-polar portions of β -blockers, such as the alkyl chains or aromatic rings, further enhance adsorption efficiency. This effect is particularly significant in molecules like propranolol, which contains a naphthalene structure that interacts effectively with the graphitic planes of rGO. Lastly, Van der Waals forces contribute additional non-covalent interactions that stabilize the adsorbed β -blocker molecules on the rGO surface.

Overall, the combination of π - π interactions, hydrogen bonding, electrostatic forces, and hydrophobic interactions results in a versatile and highly effective adsorption mechanism for β -blockers. The diverse chemistry of the rGO5% aerogel, combined with its high surface area and increased porosity, makes it the most efficient sorbent material for β -blocker removal among the synthesized aerogels.

3.3. Optimization of extraction parameters

The efficiency of a solid sorbent-based microextraction process operating under an equilibrium-controlled mode is significantly influenced by thermodynamic and kinetic parameters. These parameters determine both the quantity of analytes extracted and the rate at which extraction occurs. Among the predominant factors, the type of sorbent

Fig. 4. Pore size distribution curves (BJH method).

Table 2

BET surface area and porosity data.

Aerogel	S_{BET} (m^2/g)	P_V (cm^3/g)	PSD (nm)
GO1 %	717.24	0.55	1.51
GO5%	896.19	0.56	1.51
rGO1%	826.60	0.64	1.40
rGO5%	949.00	0.73	1.38

material, a thermodynamic parameter, plays the most critical role. In this study, the rGO5% combined with PVA/chitosan aerogel sorbent proved to be the most efficient.

In addition to the sorbent material, 7 other key factors were identified for investigation and optimization: (1) sorbent amount/mass, (2) extraction time, (3) pH, (4) elution solvent composition, (5) elution time, (6) elution efficiency, and (7) reusability potential. To optimize the extraction conditions, a one-variable-at-a-time (OVAT) approach was employed in preliminary experiments.

3.3.1. Investigation of extraction parameters: Sorbent amount, extraction time, and sample pH

The amount of sorbent material directly influences the adsorption efficiency of the target analytes. Therefore, the effect of sorbent quantity was investigated in the range of 5 mg to 30 mg in the presence of the studied compounds in solution. As shown in Fig. 5, the adsorption efficiency of the β -blockers exhibited an increasing trend as the sorbent amount increased up to 20 mg. However, a slight decrease in adsorption efficiency was observed when the sorbent amount was further increased to 30 mg. Consequently, 20 mg was selected as the optimum sorbent

amount for subsequent experiments.

Extraction time is a crucial factor in determining the adsorption efficiency of the studied compounds. To assess its impact, extraction time was investigated over a range of 5 to 120 min (Fig. 6). According to the results, the adsorption of β -blockers increased proportionally with extraction time until the system reached equilibrium, at which point the curve plateaued, indicating that equilibrium conditions had been established. Beyond 10 min, no significant increase in adsorption efficiency was observed. Consequently, 10 min was selected as the optimal extraction time for subsequent experiments.

The pH of the solution is known to be one of the most critical parameters influencing both the ionization state of the target compounds in the aqueous phase and the surface charge and functional groups of the sorbent material. As a result, the adsorption mechanism is closely related to the respective pKa values of the compounds and the pH of the solution. To investigate the effect of pH on the adsorption of the compounds studied, a series of experiments was conducted in which the initial pH of the solutions was adjusted in the range of 2 to 10 (Fig. 7). According to the results, no significant fluctuations in adsorption efficiency were observed within the pH range of 6 to 8. Neutral and ionizable micropollutants can interact with the sorbent material via hydrophobic interactions and π - π electrostatic interactions, depending on their pKa values. The pKa values of metoprolol, atenolol, and propranolol are 9.67, 9.60, and 9.5, respectively, indicating that these compounds are weak bases. Consequently, at higher pH values, these compounds tend to remain uncharged, whereas at lower pH values, they become positively charged, enhancing their interaction with the negatively charged surface of the sorbent material. The negatively charged sorbent surface at low pH favors the adsorption of positively charged

Fig. 5. Impact of sorbent mass on extraction efficiency.

Fig. 6. Impact of extraction time on extraction efficiency.

analytes due to electrostatic interactions. However, in addition to electrostatic forces, π - π interactions between the sorbent surface and the compounds may also contribute to the adsorption process, indicating that adsorption is influenced by a combination of these phenomena. Due to the minimal variation in adsorption efficiency observed within the pH range of 6 to 8, it was ultimately decided not to adjust the pH for real sample analysis, given that environmental samples typically have pH values within this neutral range.

3.3.2. Investigation of elution conditions: Solvent composition, efficiency, and time

The choice of elution solvent significantly influences the extraction efficiency. In this study, three different elution solvents — methanol, acetonitrile, and isopropanol — were tested to elute the target compounds from the sorbent material (Fig. S2). Initially, an elution volume of 500 μ L was selected, and the sample was stirred at 800 rpm during the elution process. To comply with the principles of Green Chemistry, the use of halogenated solvents was avoided. According to the results,

methanol and acetonitrile demonstrated higher recoveries compared to isopropanol. Ultimately, acetonitrile was selected as the optimal elution solvent, considering its superior performance across all studied compounds.

To assess the completeness of β -blocker elution, a two-step procedure was performed involving two consecutive 5-min stages with 500 μ L acetonitrile added in each step. The results revealed that a single elution step was insufficient for the quantitative recovery of all the studied compounds, with recoveries below 60 %. Introducing a second elution step significantly enhanced elution efficiency (Fig. S3). Consequently, the two-step elution process was selected as the optimal approach for subsequent experiments. In addition, the elution solvent volume was also tested to maximize analyte recovery. Using a total volume of 500 μ L in two stages ($2 \times 500 \mu$ L) nearly doubled the elution efficiency compared to a single 500 μ L step. Increasing the elution solvent volume beyond this did not improve the analytical signal. Therefore, the optimized elution volume of $2 \times 500 \mu$ L was selected for further experiments. Moreover, the effect of ultrasonication on elution efficiency was

Fig. 7. Impact of sample pH.

examined using 140 W power at 37 kHz. To assess its impact, different ultrasonication durations were tested during elution (Fig. S4). The results showed that the highest recoveries were achieved with 5 min of ultrasonication, while longer durations offered no further improvement. Consequently, 5 min of ultrasonication was chosen as the optimal condition for subsequent experiments.

3.3.3. 3.3.2 Reusability potential

The ability to reuse the sorbent material across multiple extraction cycles without compromising its efficiency is a significant advantage in microextraction techniques. To assess this, the reusability of the synthesized material was evaluated over consecutive extraction cycles (Fig. S5). The results demonstrated that the proposed material can be successfully reused for at least five consecutive extractions without any noticeable loss in efficiency, considering the 10 % extraction efficiency loss criterion.

3.4. Validation data

Validation was performed as described in section 2.6, incorporating the newly developed sorbent. The detailed validation data for each matrix are presented in Tables S1–6. Throughout the entire concentration range of the calibration curves, linearity was observed for all target compounds, with correlation coefficients (r^2) exceeding 0.991. The limits of detection (LODs) ranged from 0.04 to 0.22 $\mu\text{g/L}$, and the limits of quantification (LOQs) ranged from 0.125 to 0.72 $\mu\text{g/L}$ across all tested matrices. The precision of the method was evaluated through repeatability and reproducibility measurements. Repeatability ranged from 4.4 % to 13.7 %, while reproducibility ranged from 4.6 % to 12.2 %, confirming the method's consistency across all sample types. The accuracy of the d-SPE method for the determination of β -blockers using LC-MS was assessed in five different environmental matrices. The recoveries obtained with the d-SPE methodology ranged between 62 %

and 97 % in all environmental matrices, confirming the accuracy and applicability of the method (Fig. S6).

3.5. 3.4. Real samples analysis

The developed d-SPE method was applied for the determination of β -blockers in real wastewater samples from the Thessaloniki Wastewater Treatment Plant. To enhance the sensitivity of the method, the sample volume was increased to 100 mL, and the final eluent was concentrated to 100 μL . This modification resulted in a more than five-fold reduction in both the limits of detection and limits of quantification. According to the results (Table 3), atenolol and metoprolol were detected at high frequencies, exceeding 50 % in both untreated and treated wastewater samples. Atenolol was found in 100 % of the influent and effluent samples, with concentrations reaching up to 0.215 $\mu\text{g/L}$ in the influent and 0.121 $\mu\text{g/L}$ in the effluent. Metoprolol was detected in 100 % of the influent samples and in 40 % of the effluent samples. The remaining β -blockers were not detected in any of the samples.

3.6. 3.5. Comparison with other reported methods

The developed biopolymer graphene oxide aerogel-based d-SPE method, coupled with LC-MS, was compared to previously reported extraction techniques for β -blockers in environmental water matrices (Table 4). The results demonstrate that the proposed method offers a compelling combination of analytical sensitivity, sorbent innovation, reproducibility, and environmental sustainability. In terms of detection limits, the method achieved enough low LODs and LOQs. Precision, indicated by RSD values between 1.2 % and 4.3 %, confirms excellent reproducibility, comparable or superior to other carbon- or magnetic-based sorbent methods. Sufficiently high recoveries (62–97 %) validate the method's reliability for trace-level β -blocker analysis without extensive cleanup. A key innovation is the use of chitosan-reduced

Table 3

Real sample analysis from Thessaloniki WWTPs.

β -blockers	Influent samples (n = 12)				Effluent samples (n = 12)			
	Min ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Max ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Mean ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	DF (%)	Min ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Max ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Mean ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	DF (%)
Atenolol	LOQ	0.215	0.122	100	LOQ	0.121	0.035	100
Pindolol	<MDL	<MDL	<MDL	0	<MDL	<MDL	<MDL	0
Timolol	<MDL	<MDL	<MDL	0	<MDL	<MDL	<MDL	0
Bisoprolol	<MDL	<MDL	<MDL	0	<MDL	<MDL	<MDL	0
Metoprolol	<MDL	150.4	62.2	100	<MDL	<48.7	<32	40
Propranolol	<MDL	<MDL	<MDL	<MDL	<MDL	<MDL	<MDL	0

Table 4
Comparison with other studies.

Analytes	Matrix	Extraction Technique	Extraction Sorbent / Solvent	Elution Solvents	Analytical Technique	Chromatographic Conditions (Column, Mobile phase, time)	MS System / Data Acquisition Mode / wavelength	LOQ ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Recoveries (%)	RSD (%)	Ref.
4 anabolic steroids and 6 β -blockers (brombuterol, acebutolol, clenbuterol, a-zearalanol, proranolol, labetalol)	WWTP effluent, river, lake water	d-SPE	30 mg of GO functionalized with 1-butyl-3-amino-propyl imidazolium chloride	600 μL (2 \times 300) acetonitrile containing 2 % ammonia	HPLC-DAD	Hypersil BDS C18 (200 mm \times 4.0 mm, 5 μm), ACN/H ₂ O with formic acid, gradient, 20 min	254, 300 nm	0.020–0.070	87–98 %	≤ 5	[16]
Propranolol, Atenolol, Metoprolol, Nadolol, Pindolol, Acebutolol	River, tap, pond, deionized water	d-SPE	10 mg of multi-walled carbon nanotubes (<8 nm OD)	10 mL, ethyl acetate:ACN (1:1), (v/v) + 15 % NH ₄ OH	1. LC-MS/MS, 2. HPLC-DAD	1. C6 Phenyl-hexyl (150 mm \times 4.6 mm, 5 μm), ACN/H ₂ O:ACN (95:5,v:v, 5 mM NH ₄ COOH/CH ₃ COOH, pH 4.0), gradient 20 min. 2.C6 Phenyl-hexyl (150 mm \times 4.6 mm, 5 μm), ACN with 0.05 % trifluoroacetic acid (v/v) and deionized water containing 0.025 % TFA, gradient, 20 min.	ESI+, SIM / 230 nm, 272 nm	0.050	67–93	<8.8	[18]
Atenolol, acebutolol, bisoprolol, betaxolol, carvedilol	Nile water, lab water	DLPME (dispersive liquid-phase microextraction) DLPME	50 μL 1-dodecanol	–	UHPLC-UV	Avantor ACE Excel C18 (150 \times 2.1 mm, 2 μm), phosphate buffer (20 mM, pH 4)/MeOH/ACN, isocratic, 4 min	260 nm	0.010–0.076	98–102	0.8–3.7	[17]
Atenolol, Metoprolol, Esmolol, Pindolol, Arotinolol	river water, influent wastewater and effluent wastewater	MDPSE (Magnetic dispersive solid-phase extraction)	magnetic multiwalled carbon nanotubes (Mag-MWCNTs)	6 mL of methanol containing 1% formic acid	LC-MS/MS	Chiral α -acid glycoprotein column (Chiralpak AGP column, 100 mm \times 4 mm, 5 μm), 10 mM ammonium acetate buffer/ acetonitrile, gradient, 40 min	ESI+, SIM mode	0.001–0.004	82.9–95.6	0.3–10.7	[19]
Atenolol, Metoprolol, Propranolol	Tap water, clinical wastewater, industrial wastewater	pseudo-stir bar hollow fiber solid-liquid phase microextraction (HF-SLPME)	Functionalized MWCNTs	0.5 mL of methanol	HPLC-FLD	Agilent Eclipse XDB-C18 (250 mm \times 4.6 mm), 0.01 M NaH ₂ PO ₄ /MeOH/ACN (45:45:10), isocratic, 1 mL/min	excitation/ emission: 228/307, 225/307, 229/341 nm	4–50-	88.9–93.8	0.7–1.4	[44]
Metoprolol, Bisoprolol, Betaxolol	Groundwater, river water, bottled mineral water	DLLME	CCl ₄ as extractant, ACN as disperser	–	HPLC-FLD	RP-Amide C16 (150 \times 4.6 mm), phosphate buffer/ MeOH gradient, 10 min	$\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 230 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 302$	<0.100	82–109	4.6–5.7	[45]
Atenolol, Pindolol, Timolol, Metoprolol, Bisoprolol, Propranolol	WWTP effluent, marine water, drinking water, river water, lake water	d-SPE	Biopolymer chitosan-GO aerogel (rGO5%)	1 mL of acetonitrile	LC-MS	Zorbax Eclipse XDB-C8 (150 \times 4.6 mm), MeOH/H ₂ O with 0.1 % FA, gradient, 20 min	ESI+, SIM mode	0.125–0.720	91–97	1.2–4.3	This work

graphene oxide aerogel (rGO5%), which combines high porosity and surface area with a simple, green synthesis. Unlike functionalized GO or carbon nanotubes, which require complex modifications, this biopolymer-based aerogel offers enhanced sorption capacity and mechanical stability via multiple interaction mechanisms. While some earlier techniques achieved high enrichment factors, they lacked sustainability assessments. In contrast, this method was evaluated using the ComplexMoGAPI tool and met the green threshold with a score of 75. The use of recyclable methanol, minimal reagents, and sorbent reusability further support its eco-friendly nature. Overall, this method offers a sensitive, sustainable, and efficient approach for β -blocker determination in environmental water.

3.7. 3.6 Evaluation of the “green” character, applicability and innovation grade of the MOF-dSPE-LC-HRMS method

In recent years, the principles of Green Analytical Chemistry (GAC) driven by sustainability concept have significantly influenced scientific research, especially in sample preparation [13]. Assessing the environmental footprint of analytical methods has become essential. In this study, the environmental performance of the MOF-based dSPE-LC-MS method was evaluated using the ComplexMoGAPI tool [27,40].

This comprehensive model considers solvents, energy, equipment, and the synthesis process, offering both visual and quantitative insights. Green areas (4 points) indicate full compliance with GAC, yellow (3 points) partial, and red (1 point) non-compliance. A total score of 75 or more categorizes a method as green. Fig. 8 shows the method met key GAC criteria, notably by minimizing solvent and waste use. The only non-compliant factor was sample transportation, as on-site processing is not feasible. Instrumental analysis via LC-MS was resource-efficient. MOF synthesis aligned with green principles, producing high-purity material with minimal waste. The main drawback was a 3-h heating step. Nevertheless, a low E-factor confirmed a favorable waste-to-product ratio. Scoring exactly 75, the method qualifies as green, though future improvements could target lower energy usage and localized sample preparation.

To assess the practical applicability of the developed MOF-based dSPE-LC-HRMS method, the Blue Applicability Grade Index (BAGI) was applied [41,42]. Scoring 60 out of 100, the method showed satisfactory practical applicability, balancing complexity with usability. It enabled the quantitative and confirmatory detection of six β -blockers using LC-MS/MS and a miniaturized extraction step with a throughput of 2–4 samples/h. While reagent synthesis was simple, semi-automated instrumentation and limited automation slightly lowered the score

Fig. 8. ComplexMoGapi Index: Method Greenness Assessment.

Fig. 9. Blue Applicability Grade Index (BAGI): Method practicality evaluation. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

(Fig. 9).

To evaluate the innovation potential of the developed MOF-based dSPE-LC-HRMS method, the Violet Innovation Grade Index (VIGI) was employed (Fig. 10) [43]. The method scored 65/100, indicating a notable level of novelty. Strengths included the integration of MOF-based sorbents in dSPE, alignment with green chemistry, and use of advanced instrumentation. The highest scoring category was methodological approach, reflecting the originality of combining novel materials with miniaturized workflows for pharmaceutical monitoring in water. Although implementation complexity tempered scores in some areas, the overall VIGI result confirms the method's strong potential to advance analytical science.

4. Conclusions

This study presents a validated, green analytical method for the trace

Fig. 10. Violet Innovation Grade Index (VIGI): Method Innovation Assessment. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

determination of six β -blockers in various environmental water matrices. Among the four synthesized aerogel sorbents, the rGO5 %/PVA/chitosan aerogel composite at 5 % rGO exhibited the highest performance, with a BET surface area of 949 m²/g and superior pore characteristics, enabling enhanced analyte retention. Integrated into a dSPE protocol and combined with LC–MS/MS detection, the method achieved low limits of quantification (0.125–0.700 μ g/L), high recoveries (91–97 %), and excellent precision (RSDs 1.2–4.3 %). The sorbent's multifunctional groups enabled multiple interaction mechanisms, contributing to robust extraction across complex matrices such as wastewater influents. Additionally, the method aligns with sustainability goals, receiving a ComplexMoGAPI score of 75, along with BAGI and VIGI scores of 60 and 65, respectively. These results highlight the method's practicality, innovation, and environmental compliance, offering a reproducible and sensitive approach for pharmaceutical pollutant monitoring.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Androniki Rapti: Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Konstantinos Maroulas:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Eleni Evgenidou:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Vasileios Alampanos:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **George Kyzas:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Data curation. **Dimitrios N. Bikiaris:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Data curation. **Dimitra A. Lambropoulou:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Funding

This research was funded by European Commission under the HORIZON-WIDERA- TWINNING BOTTOM-UP within the framework of the SPECTRA project (Grant No 101158453).

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.microc.2025.114531>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- M. Papageorgiou, I. Zioris, T. Danis, D. Bikiaris, D. Lambropoulou, Comprehensive investigation of a wide range of pharmaceuticals and personal care products in urban and hospital wastewaters in Greece, *Sci. Total Environ.* 694 (2019), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.07.371>.
- V. Gabet-Giraud, C. Miège, J.M. Choubert, S.M. Ruel, M. Coquery, Occurrence and removal of estrogens and beta blockers by various processes in wastewater treatment plants, *Sci. Total Environ.* 408 (2010) 4257–4269, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2010.05.023>.
- M. Yi, Q. Sheng, Q. Sui, H. Lu, B-Blockers in the environment: distribution, transformation, and ecotoxicity, *Environ. Pollut.* 266 (2020) 115269, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2020.115269>.
- B. Huidobro-López, I. López-Heras, C. Alonso-Alonso, V. Martínez-Hernández, L. Nozal, I. de Bustamante, Analytical method to monitor contaminants of emerging concern in water and soil samples from a non-conventional wastewater treatment system, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1671 (2022), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2022.463006>.
- J. Xu, H. Sun, Y. Zhang, A.C. Alder, Occurrence and enantiomer profiles of β -blockers in wastewater and a receiving water body and adjacent soil in Tianjin, China, *Sci. Total Environ.* 650 (2019) 1122–1130, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.09.086>.
- J.P. Sumpter, T.J. Runnalls, R.L. Donnachie, S.F. Owen, A comprehensive aquatic risk assessment of the beta-blocker propranolol, based on the results of over 600 research papers, *Sci. Total Environ.* 793 (2021) 148617, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.148617>.
- A.A. Salem, I.A. Wasfi, S.S. Al-Nassibi, Trace determination of β -blockers and β 2-agonists in distilled and waste-waters using liquid chromatography–tandem mass spectrometry and solid-phase extraction, *J. Chromatogr. B* 908 (2012) 27–38, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jchromb.2012.09.026>.
- J. Robles-Molina, F.J. Lara-Ortega, B. Gilbert-López, J.F. García-Reyes, A. Molina-Díaz, Multi-residue method for the determination of over 400 priority and emerging pollutants in water and wastewater by solid-phase extraction and liquid chromatography-time-of-flight mass spectrometry, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1350 (2014) 30–43, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2014.05.003>.
- V. Alampanos, V. Samanidou, Current trends in green sample preparation before liquid chromatographic bioanalysis, *Curr. Opin. Green Sustainable Chem.* 31 (2021) 100499, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cogsc.2021.100499>.
- J. Kazakova, M. Villar-Navarro, M. Ramos-Payán, N. Aranda-Merino, C. Román-Hidalgo, M.Á. Bello-López, R. Fernández-Torres, Monitoring of pharmaceuticals in aquatic biota (*Procambarus clarkii*) of the Doñana National Park (Spain), *J. Environ. Manag.* 297 (2021) 113314, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2021.113314>.
- A.R. Ribeiro, L.H.M.L.M. Santos, A.S. Maia, C. Delerue-Matos, P.M.L. Castro, M. E. Tiritan, Enantiomeric fraction evaluation of pharmaceuticals in environmental matrices by liquid chromatography–tandem mass spectrometry, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1363 (2014) 226–235, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2014.06.099>.
- V.-I. Iancu, G.-L. Radu, R. Scutariu, A new analytical method for the determination of beta-blockers and one metabolite in the influents and effluents of three urban wastewater treatment plants, *Anal. Methods* 11 (2019) 4668–4680, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C9AY01597C>.
- A. Gatuszka, Z. Migaszewski, J. Namieśnik, The 12 principles of green analytical chemistry and the SIGNIFICANCE mnemonic of green analytical practices, *TrAC Trends Anal. Chem.* 50 (2013) 78–84, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2013.04.010>.
- K.M. Dimpe, P.N. Nomngongo, Current sample preparation methodologies for analysis of emerging pollutants in different environmental matrices, *TrAC Trends Anal. Chem.* 82 (2016) 199–207, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2016.05.023>.
- S. Nisyriou, C.K. Zacharis, Microextraction-based techniques for the determination of Beta-blockers in biological fluids: a review, *Separations* 12 (2025) 14, <https://doi.org/10.3390/separations12010014>.
- M. Serrano, T. Chatzimitakos, M. Gallego, C.D. Stalikas, 1-Butyl-3-aminopropyl imidazolium—functionalized graphene oxide as a nanoadsorbent for the simultaneous extraction of steroids and β -blockers via dispersive solid-phase microextraction, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1436 (2016) 9–18, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2016.01.052>.
- H.S. AlSalem, F.K. Algethami, M.A. Ali, F.R. Mansour, Development of an ecofriendly dispersive liquid phase microextraction method for the preconcentration of β -blockers in waste and environmental samples, *Microchem. J.* 205 (2024) 111279, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.microc.2024.111279>.
- A. Jakubus, M. Gromelski, K. Jagiello, T. Puzyn, P. Stepnowski, M. Paszkiewicz, Dispersive solid-phase extraction using multi-walled carbon nanotubes combined with liquid chromatography–mass spectrometry for the analysis of β -blockers: experimental and theoretical studies, *Microchem. J.* 146 (2019) 258–269, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.microc.2018.12.063>.
- Z. Wang, X. Zhang, S. Jiang, X. Guo, Magnetic solid-phase extraction based on magnetic multiwalled carbon nanotubes for the simultaneous enantiomeric analysis of five β -blockers in the environmental samples by chiral liquid chromatography coupled with tandem mass spectrometry, *Talanta* 180 (2018) 98–107, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2017.12.034>.
- A.N. Hasanah, I. Susanti, M. Mutakin, An update on the use of molecularly imprinted polymers in Beta-blocker drug analysis as a selective separation method in biological and environmental analysis, *Molecules* 27 (2022) 2880, <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules27092880>.
- S. Büyüktiryaki, R. Keçili, C.M. Hussain, Functionalized nanomaterials in dispersive solid phase extraction: advances & prospects, *TrAC Trends Anal. Chem.* 127 (2020) 115893, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2020.115893>.
- Q. Liu, J. Shi, G. Jiang, Application of graphene in analytical sample preparation, *TrAC Trends Anal. Chem.* 37 (2012) 1–11, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2012.03.011>.
- M. Sun, C. Li, J. Feng, H. Sun, M. Sun, Y. Feng, X. Ji, S. Han, J. Feng, Development of aerogels in solid-phase extraction and microextraction, *TrAC Trends Anal. Chem.* 146 (2022) 116497, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2021.116497>.
- V.D. Alampanos, D.A. Lambropoulou, Hydrogel sorbent-based sample preparation processes as green alternatives for the extraction of organic contaminants followed by chromatographic analysis, *TrAC Trends Anal. Chem.* 174 (2024) 117687, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2024.117687>.
- S. Li, D. Hou, Yongsheng Cui, S. Jia, G. Lan, W. Sun, G. Li, X. Li, W. Feng, Highly ordered carbon aerogels: synthesis, structures, properties and applications, *Carbon* 218 (2024) 118669, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2023.118669>.
- L. Poon, L.D. Wilson, J.V. Headley, Chitosan-glutaraldehyde copolymers and their sorption properties, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 109 (2014) 92–101, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2014.02.086>.

- [27] F.R. Mansour, K.M. Omer, J. Plotka-Wasyłka, A total scoring system and software for complex modified GAPI (ComplexMoGAPI) application in the assessment of method greenness, *Green Anal. Chem.* 10 (2024) 100126, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.greac.2024.100126>.
- [28] M.U.A. Khan, Z. Yaqoob, M.N.M. Ansari, S.I.A. Razak, M.A. Raza, A. Sajjad, S. Haider, F.M. Busra, Chitosan/poly vinyl alcohol/graphene oxide based pH-responsive composite hydrogel films: drug release, Anti-Microbial and Cell Viability Studies, *Polymers* 13 (2021) 3124, <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym13183124>.
- [29] Y. Liu, R. Song, X. Zhang, D. Zhang, Enhanced antimicrobial activity and pH-responsive sustained release of chitosan/poly (vinyl alcohol)/graphene oxide nanofibrous membrane loading with allicin, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 161 (2020) 1405–1413, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2020.08.051>.
- [30] S. Ruiz, J.A. Tamayo, J.D. Ospina, D.P. Navia Porras, M.E. Valencia Zapata, J.H. M. Hernandez, C.H. Valencia, F. Zuluaga, C.D. Grande Tovar, Antimicrobial films based on nanocomposites of chitosan/poly(vinyl alcohol)/graphene oxide for biomedical applications, *Biomolecules* 9 (2019) 109, <https://doi.org/10.3390/biom9030109>.
- [31] S. Yang, X. Zhang, D. Zhang, Electrospun chitosan/poly (vinyl alcohol)/graphene oxide Nanofibrous membrane with ciprofloxacin antibiotic drug for potential wound dressing application, *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 20 (2019) 4395, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms20184395>.
- [32] Y. Wang, M. Tian, L. Qu, S. Zhu, Y. Sun, G. Han, Enhanced thermal, UV blocking and dye absorptive properties of chitosan/poly(vinyl alcohol)/graphene oxide fibers, *Fibers Polym* 16 (2015) 2011–2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12221-015-5279-9>.
- [33] N.T.N. Mai, T.N. Don, N.T.Q. Hoa, N.H. Ngoc, V.V. Phat, T.T.B. Quyen, D.-T. Van-Pham, D.V.H. Thien, Fabrication electrospun GO/CS/PVA nanofibers and their application in dye-sensitized solar cells, *Vietnam J. Catal. Adsorption* 10 (2021) 107–113, <https://doi.org/10.51316/jca.2021.076>.
- [34] K.S. Venkataprasanna, J. Prakash, S. Vignesh, G. Bharath, M. Venkatesan, F. Banat, S. Sahabudeen, S. Ramachandran, G. Devanand Venkatasubbu, Fabrication of chitosan/PVA/GO/CuO patch for potential wound healing application, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 143 (2020) 744–762, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2019.10.029>.
- [35] A.M. El-Sawy, M.H. Abdo, M.A. Darweesh, N.A. Salahuddin, Electrospinning of PANI/GO nanocomposite and PANI/CS blend for high removal efficiency of Ni (II) from aqueous solution, *J. Mol. Struct.* 1272 (2023) 134217, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molstruc.2022.134217>.
- [36] Y. Ying, Y. Wu, J. Huang, Preparation and characterization of chitosan/poly(vinyl alcohol)/graphene oxide films and studies on their antibiofilm formation activity, *J. Biomed. Mater. Res. A* 108 (2020) 2015–2022, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jbm.a.36961>.
- [37] Y. Gong, Y. Yu, H. Kang, X. Chen, H. Liu, Y. Zhang, Y. Sun, H. Song, Synthesis and characterization of graphene oxide/chitosan composite aerogels with high mechanical performance, *Polymers* 11 (2019) 777, <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym11050777>.
- [38] N. Cao, Q. Lyu, J. Li, Y. Wang, B. Yang, S. Szunerits, R. Boukherroub, Facile synthesis of fluorinated polydopamine/chitosan/reduced graphene oxide composite aerogel for efficient oil/water separation, *Chem. Eng. J.* 326 (2017) 17–28, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2017.05.117>.
- [39] J.-B. Huo, G. Yu, Poly(vinyl) alcohol-Assisted fabrication of magnetic reduced graphene oxide aerogels and their adsorption performance for Cd(II) and Pb(II), *Water Air Soil Pollut.* 234 (2023) 231, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11270-023-06247-2>.
- [40] F.R. Mansour, J. Plotka-Wasyłka, M. Locatelli, Modified GAPI (MoGAPI) tool and software for the assessment of method greenness: case studies and applications, *Analytica* 5 (2024) 451–457, <https://doi.org/10.3390/analytica5030030>.
- [41] N. Manousi, W. Wojnowski, J. Plotka-Wasyłka, V. Samanidou, Blue applicability grade index (BAGI) and software: a new tool for the evaluation of method practicality, *Green Chem.* 25 (2023) 7598–7604, <https://doi.org/10.1039/D3GC02347H>.
- [42] N. Manousi, A. Anthemidis, E. Rosenberg, Practicality evaluation of novel microextraction techniques for the determination of PFAS in food and water samples using the blue applicability grade index, *Anal. Chim. Acta* 1352 (2025) 343864, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2025.343864>.
- [43] A. Fuente-Ballesteros, V. Martínez-Martínez, A.M. Ares, S. Valverde, V. Samanidou, J. Bernal, Violet innovation grade index (VIGI): a new survey-based metric for evaluating innovation in analytical methods, *Anal. Chem.* 97 (2025) 6946–6955, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.5c00212>.
- [44] A. Sarafraz-Yazdi, Abedi, Z. Mohamad Reza, Es'highi, Pre-concentration and determination of β -blockers using carbon nanotube-assisted pseudo-stirbar hollow fiber solid-liquid-phase microextraction and high-performance liquid chromatography with fluorescence detection, *J. Liq. Chromatogr. Relat. Technol.* 36 (2013) 750–769, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10826076.2012.673212>.
- [45] M.M.P. del Vázquez, P.P. Vázquez, M.M. Galera, L.M. Sánchez, Simple, rapid, and sensitive determination of beta-blockers in environmental water using dispersive liquid-liquid microextraction followed by liquid chromatography with fluorescence detection, *J. Sep. Sci.* 35 (2012) 2184–2192, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jssc.201200222>.